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A STUDY ON PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AND STUDENT'S ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AT THE SECONDARY LEVEL IN GILGIT-BALTISTAN

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Abstract

Parental involvement and its impacts on academic achievement is an interesting debate among educationists. So this study was planned which intended to find out the relationship between parental involvement and students' academic achievement. A mixed-method research design was used to execute the research. To achieve the objectives of the study all the students of secondary schools in Gilgit-Baltistan and their parents were treated as a population of the study. The study was delimited to District Skardu. The researcher used a multi-stage sampling technique and selected 214 students of the 9th class from 12 secondary schools in Gilgit-Baltistan. Parents of selected students were also interviewed. The tools for the data collection were a questionnaire and interviews. The questionnaire consisted of 28 positive statements regarding parental involvement. The responses to the questionnaire were analyzed through Pearson Moment Product Correlation. The researcher found a significant positive relationship between parental involvement and students' academic achievement. The outcomes of parents' responses represented that parents of secondary school children help their children by providing them with a suitable home environment and by providing them with educational facilities. Illiteracy was found as the main obstacle which avoids parental involvement. Children's Academic achievement increases when parents are involved in their children's education. It is recommended that future studies may be planned to research those students who belong to broken families, single parents, and step-parents, and their impact on the academic achievement of their step-sons or daughters.

Keywords: Parental Involvement, Academic Achievement, Gilgit-Baltistan, Secondary Schools, Children's education

Introduction:

The world has become an extremely globalized economy; the students who graduated from high school should have sufficient skills so that they can contribute to the market. In developed countries, policymakers are now focusing on reducing the gap between low and high academic achievement so that the majority of students can participate in a country's development. They identified parental involvement as the most influencing factor as in only academic achievement (Easton, 2010).

Any society cannot be developed without education. For the development of any society, education is necessary. One of the major functions of education is to socialize the children, and parents play a vital role in the socialization process. Mostly parents are accountable to socialize their children for making them educated members of their nation. Parents have a central role to enhance their children's education. Without parents' proper guidance and assistance, students cannot be able to achieve their academic goals and aims. According to Dixon (1992), "Parental involvement in almost any form creates measurable gains in student achievement".

There are plenty of studies that identified children whose parents mostly participate in their children's learning get the high academic achievement while those children get low marks whose parents are less involved in their children learning (Fan, 2001).

When parents take interest and get involved in their children's school activities it is called parent involvement. It is an obligation of parents to their time, helpfulness, liveliness and concern to contribute to their children's success. Research discoveries recommend that the concern of parents alongside their actions and attitude toward their children's schooling influence students' achievement (Huang and Mason, 2008).

We cannot describe parent involvement to any specific aspect only but it includes all

aspects from schooling to the progress of children throughout their academic life, identifying that the first and basic inspiration in children's life is their parents. There are many kinds of Parent involvement:

- When there is two-way communication among parents and schools concerning their children's progress in school
- Taking parents as fundamental educators and important agents for their children's learning
- Participation of parents towards their children's school and home activities voluntarily
- The decision-making of parents about their children's learning, well-being, and health
- The school's aspiration is reflected by cooperating with community administrations for children.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of the study was to find out the role of parents in their children learning at the secondary level.

Significance of the study

It would be helpful for parents and future researchers to understand the importance of parental involvement.

Objectives

The objectives of the study were:

1. To find out the relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement.
2. To assess parental involvement in their children's learning at the secondary level in GB.

Research Questions

- RQ 1. What is the relationship between parental involvement in the academic achievement of students?
- RQ 2. How parental involvement is affecting the student's learning at the secondary level in GB?

Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant relationship between parental involvement and the academic achievement of children.

H₁: There is a positive relationship between parental involvement and students' academic achievement.

Literature Review:

Studies have demonstrated that there is a positive relationship between the academic results of students and the involvement of parents. The suggestions from various researchers have demonstrated that parents, who took a dynamic interest in a child's learning at home, indicated good results. Mother and father ought to give a motivating and persuading home environment to expand the enthusiasm of their child in educational practices. They ought to make a good and competitive home environment to use the hidden abilities and capacities of the child. All the members of a family ought to add to make a helpful learning environment for learners at home (Chaudhry et al., 2015).

Parental inclusion refers to the measure of interest a parent has in educating her/his kid. A few schools foster sound parental contribution through different occasions and volunteer open doors, but at times it's up to the parents to include themselves in their children's education. When parents know about up-to-date curricula and the activities happening in the classroom they can contribute well to their child's education.

Parental contribution to education has been a subject of passion for different years among individuals who are anxious about enhancing learning accomplishment for their children (Dempsey and Sandler, 1995). Benner & Mistry, (2007) noted that economically well parents are concerned about their children's academic performance and not their creative potential

Rahman (2001) has research concluded parent and child interaction lays a firm foundation for academic achievement. The stronger the relationships, especially as they

relate to educational issues, the higher the academic achievement

The most precise predictor of a student's achievement in school is not income or social status, but the extent to which that student's family can create a good home environment that encourages learning of children, the high communication level between parents and child, yet reasonable and sensible, expectations for the child's accomplishment and future professions and become involved in the society. Velez and Jones accentuate that parental desires and expectations are identified with educational achievement. Parents' expectations towards their children learning success are absolutely and positively related to grades in Science, Math, and English. There is likewise a solid relationship between parents who uphold rules at home and their child's grades at school (Rahman, 2001).

Parents' child communication, contact with the school, volunteering, and finding that instructive goals applied the most grounded beneficial outcome on secondary school student's educational success and that contact with the school demonstrated a negative impact. Sui Chu & Willms (1996) utilized a comparable arrangement of parental association composites of home discussion between parents and children, home supervision, communication with school and school support and discovered comparative results for eighth-grade students. Discussion at home had the most grounded effect on the outcome of eighth-class students on standardized test scores, while school communication with the school had a slightly negative impact (Sui Chu and Willms, 1996).

Blud (2002) saw a positive and agreeable relationship between family contribution and learner's success, behavioural, and social modification while the educational level or social status of a student's parent does not affect academic success.

Positive impacts of the involvement of parents in schools have been shown at both the eighth and ninth, tenth grades over a few studies, with the biggest impacts regularly happening at the elementary level (Jeyne, 2005), (Jeynes, 2007), (Stewart, E. B. 2008).

A recent meta-investigation demonstrated that the involvement of parents in the school life of their children was all the more definitely connected with high grades and academics for learners than assisting with homework (Hill, N. E. and Tyson, D. F, 2009).

Methodology

The research methodology is the deliberate hypothetical investigation of the methodology connected to a field of study. The research design and methodology help researchers to solve research problem step by step. The descriptive survey research design was used for this study. The major purpose of the study was to find out parental involvement and students' academic achievement. The population of the study consisted of around 235 secondary schools in Gilgit-Baltistan. There were 30 secondary schools in District Skardu out of which 16 were boys' secondary schools and 14 were girls' secondary schools. The researcher selected 12 schools and selected 214 students. There were 28 items in the tool regarding parental involvement. All the statements of the parental involvement questionnaire for students were positive (in favour of Parental involvement) so that marked consistency as 3, 2, 1 for agree, neutral and disagree. The researchers personally visited 12 Government Secondary schools in the district of Skardu for the collection of data. A mixed method approach was used to find out the objectives and research questions of the research. The researcher personally administered the questionnaires to the students by visiting the 9th class of each sampled school and the researcher helped students where they felt difficulty in understanding the questionnaire. After the collection of data, the data regarding parents'

involvement in their children's learning was analyzed through Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used to find the relationship between parental involvement and students' academic achievement. The researcher calculated the correlation by using the product-moment correlation coefficient. In this study, the researcher calculated parental involvement scores (summing up all responses) of students with exam scores (academic achievement) to find the value of "r" (correlation coefficient) which indicates a correlation, in social sciences the value of r is always less than 1 because 1 indicates perfect correlation which is impossible in social sciences.

FINDINGS

Analyses of responses of parents against three open-ended questions which were related to the contribution of parents towards their children's academic achievement

In the first part responses of parents regarding their role in the academic progress of their children are tabulated towards three open-ended items. The responses of 184 parents of ninth-class students are quantified to examine the frequency of frequent responses against every item; they were arranged after calculating the percentage, whereas the responses with low rates were also added in the analysis for more elucidation of the response rate against each item. The below steps were followed to analyze the responses of parents in the form of qualitative data given in three open-ended questions.

Step 1: Reducing the statement of each question into a theme

In the first step, three statements of each open-ended question were converted into a single logical theme which is stated below

- 1) Parents' help in their child's studies
- 2) Problems being faced by parents when they are helping their children
- 3) Positive changes in children's academic achievement when parents are involved in their learning

Step 2: A deep and careful study of all responses

A careful study of all responses of parents was done to assess parental involvement in

		AA	PI
AA	Pearson correlation	1	.443**
	Significant	214	.000
	N		214
PI	Pearson correlation	.443**	1
	Significant	.000	214
	N	214	

their children learning at the secondary level.

Step 3: Development of response categories

The responses against three open-ended questions were altered into suitable response categories.

In the following table, the education status of participants (parents) is shown:

Table 1. Frequencies of parents' education level.

Education Level	Frequency	Percentage
Illiterate	72	40.8%
Primary	20	10.8%
Middle	15	8.2%
Matric	27	14.67%
Intermediate	22	12%
Graduation	18	9.8%
Masters	7	3.80%

Some parents said they help their children by sending them to tuition or providing them with home tuition, they also give rewards and punishments to their children for their academic growth. The elder siblings also seem helping secondary school students with their homework and studies.

The majority of parents don't visit school. They don't involve in their children's learning. The main barriers to parental involvement at the secondary level are illiteracy, there aren't a sufficient number of schools in district Skardu, due to which distance from school and home avoid parents to visit their children's schools. Fathers have more concern about their children's education as compared to mothers, as Skardu is a hilly area so women have to do domestic tasks and fieldwork as

well, which prevents mothers from get involve in their children's learning. Responses of participants indicated that when parents get involved in their child's education they see positive changes in academic achievement and their child gets encouragement and confidence.

The correlation of two independent variables (parental involvement) and students' academic achievement was calculated concerning the research objective.

Table 2: Positive impacts of parental involvement on children's academic achievement.

Sr. No	Response Categories	Frequency	%
1	Good marks	62	28.97
2	Confidence	37	17.29
3	Encouragement	61	28.50
4	Interest in studies	24	11.21
5	No response	30	14.02

In Table 6 the responses of parents of secondary school children of District Skardu regarding the positive changes in academic achievement when they are involved in their children's learning are categorized into five levels. The percentages of responses are Good marks (28.97%), Encouragement (28.50%), Confidence (17.29%), and Interest in studies (11.21%) while no response (14.02).

Table 3. Relationship of Parental Involvement and Student's Academic Achievement.

The correlation coefficient of +0.4 showed positive correlations between parental involvement scores and academic achievement scores. As the sample size was 214, the degree of freedom was N-2 (212). The critical r value at 0.05, as given in the statistic book, is 0.2 and "r" at 0.01 is 0.25. Therefore, the correlation between Parental involvement and students' academic achievement is not only positive and significant at 0.05 but also at 0.01 levels of significance. The null hypothesis of this study was rejected and the research hypothesis was supported, meaning thereby that greater parental involvement is

associated with greater academic achievement and vice versa.

Part 3. Correlation Analyses

The correlation of two independent variables (parental involvement) and students' academic achievement was calculated concerning the third research objective to check the following research hypotheses.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between parental involvement and the academic achievement of children.

H₁: There is a positive relationship between parental involvement and students' academic achievement.

In the table, the correlation coefficient of +0.4 showed a positive correlation between parental involvement scores and academic achievement scores. As the sample size was 214, the degree of freedom was N₋₂ (212). The critical r value at 0.05, as given in the statistic book, is 0.2 and "r" at 0.01 is 0.25. Therefore, the correlation between Parental involvement and students' academic achievement is not only positive and significant at 0.05 but also at 0.01 levels of significance. The null hypothesis of this study was rejected and the research hypothesis was supported, meaning thereby that greater parental involvement is associated with greater academic achievement and vice versa.

The correlation coefficient was +0.4 which shows a positive correlation between parental involvement and academic achievement.

1. The correlation between Parental involvement and students' academic achievement is not only positive and significant at 0.05 but also at 0.01 levels of significance.
2. The null hypothesis of this study was rejected and the research hypothesis was supported, meaning thereby that greater parental involvement is associated with greater academic achievement and vice versa.

Conclusion

There is a positive relationship between parental involvement and students' academic achievement. Despite being illiterate parents want their children to be successful in academic life. A majority of parents do their best to provide educational facilities to their children. Due to illiteracy, parents hesitate to participate in PTMs although school principals and teachers always welcome parents to school. According to the education department of District Skardu, the literacy rate during 1998 was approximately total 34.37% of which 52% was male while the female literacy rate was 14.57% which shows the illiteracy rate was high. Now it is estimated that Gilgit Baltistan has a 65.60% literacy rate but parents' involvement in their children's education is found low. Overall the study found that parental involvement has a strong influence on academic achievement, both are complimentary to each other and these are directly proportional to each other. Parents' involvement in healthy educational activities results in better academic achievement.

Recommendations

The inclusion of parents in their children's learning is becoming day by day more important. Societies are becoming aware of the fact that parents' involvement can make education better. These secondary-level students will become successful members of society, they will serve the nation as well in future. The following recommendations are proposed by keeping in view the findings and conclusions of the study.

- 1- The provision of a good home environment or sending children for tuition is not enough for effective learning of children. Parents should get themselves involved in their children learning by playing an active role in their schooling as well. It is recommended that community, society, school and media groups should play their role to create awareness regarding parental involvement in their children's learning.

- 2- There should be strong communication between student's parents and teachers as well as there is a need for good coordination between parents, school and community for fruitful learning of learners.
- 3- To increase parental involvement school principals should arrange the best parent's award which would help increase parental involvement.
- 4- Parental involvement and students' academic achievement were found to have a positive and significant relationship. Therefore, parental involvement should be promoted by arranging seminars and media campaigns.

Here are some suggestions for future researchers

- The same study may be conducted at different levels of education and in different areas.
- The effects of parental involvement can be addressed.
- The future researcher may address a comparison of parental involvement between the public and private sectors.
- The future researcher may address a comparison of educated and uneducated mothers' involvement in their children's learning.
- It is also recommended that future studies may be planned to research those students who belong to broken families, single parents, and step-parents, and their impact on the academic achievement of their step-sons or daughters.

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